

Appendix A: Questionnaire Items of Two Measured Variables

Cognitively Deep State (Baughn & Yaprak, 1996; Pryke, 2012)

- Q1. I am committed to fulfilling my responsibilities as a young individual by promoting a healthy environment.
- Q2. I strive to contribute positively to my country by supporting efforts to maintain a healthy environment.
- Q3. I recognise my important role in ensuring the well-being of the country's environment.
- Q4. I demonstrate respect and care for the environment, believing that protecting nature is a shared responsibility.
- Q5. I acknowledge that sustainable investment can serve as a strategic tool to achieve global political supremacy while supporting the objectives of the Paris Agreement.
- Q6. I understand that the Paris Agreement requires nations to make sustainable investment decisions to safeguard the environment.
- Q7. I recognise that the connection between sustainable investment and global political influence can enhance the implementation and enforcement of the Paris Agreement.

Environmentalism (Herrera, 1992; Schlosberg, 2025)

- Q8. I can prevent environmental misuse by implementing proactive measures.
- Q9. I can help prevent further disruption to the balance of nature.
- Q10. I am committed to addressing critical environmental issues, including pollution, overpopulation, toxic waste, and the depletion of natural resources.
- Q11. I contribute to reducing pollution levels that have reached hazardous thresholds.
- Q12. I possess the knowledge to implement preventive measures that mitigate environmental pollution risks.
- Q13. I can contribute to reducing environmental issues over the next decade.
- Q14. I can inspire and influence those around me to take action in preserving the environment.
- Q15. I am mindful of my technology usage and can manage its impact on the environment.
- Q16. I can identify alternative solutions to address waste storage challenges.
- Q17. I actively contribute to conserving natural resources for future generations.
- Q18. I am willing to adapt my lifestyle and behaviour to better align with environmental sustainability, fostering a stronger connection between humans and nature.
- Q19. I can participate in decision-making processes that directly impact our lives and the environment.
- Q20. I play an active role in supporting environmental action groups in tackling various ecological challenges.
- Q21. I prioritise environmental protection in my daily actions and decisions.